

Gravimetric Determination of Copper Using Thiosalicylic Acid

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A gravimetric procedure for the determination of copper using thiosalicylic acid is reported. The method is found to be suitable for the determination of this metal in presence of zinc, iron, aluminium, nickel and cobalt. Copper in the range 10-80 mg. can be accurately determined by this procedure in the absence of these metals; whereas in their presence, copper upto 42 mg. can be determined accurately. This method can be conveniently applied in the analysis of brass.

THE application of organic reagents containing sulphur as the chelating atom is of recent interest in view of the recognition of the co-ordination capacity of sulphur atom to give rise to stronger complexes (with cations of larger ionic size), in which the back bonding from the metal ions is possible under favourable conditions.

A number of organic thiocompounds for the determination of copper are reported in literature¹⁻⁷. Most of these compounds do not have a constant composition and cannot be washed free of impurities. This necessitates ignition and weighing as oxide.

Preliminary investigations showed that thiosalicylic acid can be utilised for the gravimetric determination of copper. This reagent has been employed for the gravimetric determination of zirconium⁸ and thorium⁹. It has also been used for the colorimetric determination of palladium¹⁰, rhenium¹¹, selenium¹² and nickel¹³. The present communication describes the use of this reagent in the gravimetric determination of copper.

Experimental

A stock solution of copper was prepared by dissolving a weighed amount of AR(BDH) copper sulphate in distilled water and diluting to a known volume. The copper content was determined by the standard iodometric procedure.

A 1% solution of thiosalicylic acid in glacial acetic acid (BDH) was prepared and used after filtration.

Stock solutions of zinc, iron, nickel, cobalt and aluminium sulphates (approx. 1 ml = 5 mg., all chemicals were of analytical grade) were prepared and their effect on the determination of copper was studied.

Recommended procedure for the determination of copper:

A known volume of the standard copper sulphate solution was pipetted out into a clean beaker (250 ml) and was neutralised with sodium hydroxide. Acetic acid solution (2N) was then added drop by drop till it was faintly acidic. The solution was diluted to about 150 ml. and boiled. An excess of 1% acetic

acid solution of thiosalicylic acid was added slowly with constant stirring until the black precipitate first formed turned yellow. Finally, the solution was digested for about 15 mins. over a steam bath. The solution was tested for complete precipitation by adding a few more drops of the reagent to the supernatant liquid. Too much excess of the reagent should be avoided as the reagent itself has got the tendency of adsorbing over the precipitate. The precipitate was filtered while hot through a Whatman quantitative filter paper (No. 42, 11 cm) under suction, washed several times with hot water and finally with absolute alcohol till free from any adhering impurities. The filter was dried, strongly ignited to the oxide, cooled and weighed. The conversion to the oxide stage was effected with a drop or two of concentrated nitric acid and this treatment with nitric acid was repeated till a constant weight was obtained. The weight of the precipitate (oxide) multiplied by 0.7989 gives the weight of copper.

Results of the determination of copper recorded in Table I show that the metal could be satisfactorily determined by this reagent.

TABLE I—DETERMINATION OF COPPER USING THIOSALICYLIC ACID

Srl. No.	Copper taken (mg)	Copper found (mg)	Error %
1.	10.01	9.99	-0.20
2.	20.80	20.77	-0.14
3.	30.03	30.11	+0.27
4.	40.04	40.11	+0.17
5.	46.04	46.24	+0.43
6.	50.05	50.25	+0.40
7.	60.06	59.75	-0.52
8.	80.08	80.30	+0.27

Determination of the error of the method :

Table 2 gives results of recovery experiments. The relative mean deviation is 0.397 per cent. The

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standard deviation for a set of single measurements is 0.188 mg. The relative mean error is -0.082 per cent.

TABLE 2—DETERMINATION OF THE ERROR OF THE METHOD

Copper taken (mg)	Copper found (mg)	Error	Deviation from the mean
41.36	41.47	+0.11	0.144
41.36	41.14	-0.22	0.186
41.36	41.47	+0.11	0.144
41.36	41.30	-0.06	0.026
41.36	41.14	-0.22	0.186
41.36	41.07	-0.29	0.256
41.36	41.47	+0.11	0.144
41.36	41.55	+0.19	0.224

Determination of copper in presence of other metals :

The estimation of copper was carried out in presence of varying amounts of Zn²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺, Fe³⁺ and Al³⁺. The results are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—DETERMINATION OF COPPER IN PRESENCE OF OTHER METALS

Amount of copper taken : 41.36 mg.

Sl. No.	Added (mg)					Copper found (mg)	Error %
	Zinc	Nickel	Cobalt	Iron	Aluminium		
1.	50	—	—	—	—	41.47	+0.27
2.	100	—	—	—	—	41.14	-0.53
3.	—	20	20	—	—	41.47	+0.27
4.	—	40	40	—	—	41.55	+0.46
5.	—	—	—	5	10	41.30	-0.15
6.	—	—	—	10	20	41.07	-0.70
7.	50	30	30	5	10	41.14	-0.53
8.	50	25	25	10	20	41.47	+0.27
9.	50	—	—	5	10	41.14	-0.53
10.	50	25	25	10	—	41.30	-0.16

The results indicate that copper could be gravimetrically determined with an accuracy of ±0.70% in presence of varying amounts of zinc, nickel, cobalt, iron and aluminium. The procedure is the same as for the determination of copper excepting that in the case of iron and aluminium, a masking agent (sodium tartrate) was used to complex these two metals.

Determination of copper in brass :

Brass turnings (Ca 1.2 g) were dissolved in 50 ml. of nitric acid (1 : 1) by gradual heating. The solution was evaporated to a volume of 5 ml. on an electric hot plate. 10 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid and 10 ml. of 1 : 1 sulphuric acid were added and the solution evaporated to dense white fumes. The solution was then diluted to 100 ml. and boiled to remove oxides of nitrogen. Urea (2 g.) was added

and the solution boiled to remove traces of nitrous acid. The solution was cooled, filtered, washed well with water and made upto 250 ml. The copper content in the brass solution was then determined by the standard iodometric procedure¹⁴. One ml. of the solution contained 2.797 mg of copper.

Aliquots of the brass solution were pipetted out into a 250 ml. beaker. Sodium tartrate was then added. The solution was neutralised with ammonia and acetic acid. The copper in the solution was then determined by adopting the above procedure. Typical results are recorded in Table 4.

TABLE 4—DETERMINATION OF COPPER IN BRASS
Weight of copper (mg)

Taken	Found	Error %
13.99	14.06	+0.50
27.97	28.04	+0.25
41.96	41.86	-0.24

From the results it is evident that thiosalicylic acid can be successfully employed for the determination of copper in brass with a maximum error of ±0.5%.

Conclusion

Although thiosalicylic acid cannot give rise to a complex which can be directly weighed, it has the potentialities for accurate determination of this metal in presence of several of its associated metals.

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